

Multimodal Circuitry in Chicago’s Street Grid: Evaluating Urban Transport Network Efficiency Using Open Data

S M Redwan Kabir, Farhana Kabir Zisha

December 22, 2025

Abstract

Urban transport network efficiency is central to sustainable and equitable mobility planning. This article evaluates multimodal circuitry in Chicago to determine how well the street network accommodates driving, cycling, and walking. We use OpenStreetMap, OSMnx, and NetworkX to find the shortest pathways for 6,000 stratified origin-destination pairs divided into three modes and distance bands (0-2, 2-8, >8 km). The average circuitry is modest and densely grouped (driving 1.27, cycling 1.26, walking 1.23), with slightly higher values for short excursions and near large barriers like rivers, rail yards, and expressways. The results show good multimodal geometric efficiency and near parity between motorized and non-motorized modes, emphasizing Chicago’s grid as supportive of resilient, low-detour mobility.

Keywords: Circuitry; Multimodal transport networks; urban connectivity; Open geospatial data; Network efficiency

1 Questions

Although Chicago’s orthogonal grid is assumed to support efficient mobility (Lima et al., 2022), the degree of multimodal geometric equity has not been empirically measured. Circuitry (the ratio of network distance to straight-line distance) describes how the built street network translates into path directness (Boeing, 2022; Levinson & El-Geneidy, 2009). Prior research has compared circuitry across metropolitan areas or over time (Costa et al., 2021; Giacomini & Levinson, 2015) and linked street-network structure to spatial order and efficiency (Boeing, 2019; Cubukcu, 2020), but few studies have investigated multimodal circuitry on a shared origin-destination (OD) pair in a classic North American grid city.

This paper applies the concept of circuitry or the ratio of actual network path length over straight-line (geodesic) distance, to assess the structural efficiency of driving, cycling, and walking networks in Chicago. In this study we ask how circuitry differs across drivable, bikable, and walkable networks when all modes are evaluated on a single isotropically sampled OD set; how circuitry patterns vary by trip length (short, medium, and long straight-line distances); and what these multimodal and distance-based comparisons reveal about geometric efficiency of Chicago’s transport network?

In order to answer these questions, we create a fully reproducible workflow that employs stratified sampling by distance band, isotropic random sampling of OD nodes, and mode-specific street graphs created from OpenStreetMap. Using open data and code, this design enables us to benchmark Chicago’s multimodal circuitry and isolate geometric properties of the built network, independent of current travel demand.

2 Methods

We examine Chicago, Illinois, USA, a densely populated Midwestern city and use OpenStreetMap data accessed via the OSMnx Python library to construct three mode-specific networks—driving, cycling, and walking (Boeing, 2017); <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2017.05.004>). For each mode, we download the corresponding network within the municipal boundary and project it to a metric coordinate reference system so that edge lengths are stored in meters. For straight-line distances we retain the original latitude–longitude graphs.

To guarantee strict comparability across modes, we compute the intersection of nodes that appear in all three graphs and restrict all subsequent OD sampling to this common node set. We use an isotropic, structure-focused sampling technique in which all multimodal nodes have an equal chance of being selected since origins and destinations are taken evenly at random from the common nodes. By dispersing OD pairs throughout the urbanized area and approximating the network's geometric coverage (Costa et al., 2025), we are able to characterize the street layout's inherent efficiency rather than the need for present travel.

We first create a 120,000 pool of candidate OD pairs from the shared node set in this implementation and use geodesic formulas (via geopy) to calculate their straight-line distances in order to examine how circuitry changes with trip length. We define three distance bands based on the straight-line distance between origin and destination: short (0–2 km), medium (2–8 km), and long (>8 km), in accordance with typical ranges reported for walking and cycling (Pucher & Buehler, 2010) (and distance categories used in recent circuitry work (Costa et al., 2025)). Each candidate OD pair is assigned to one of these bands.

We then applied stratified sampling to get a balanced set of OD pairs for each band. We choose up to 2,000 OD pairs in each band at random from the candidate pool. The final stratified OD set in the Chicago case has precisely 6,000 unique OD pairs (2,000 short, 2,000 medium, and 2,000 long) because each of the three bands has more than 2,000 candidates. This single stratified OD list, with its associated geodesic distance and band label, is applied identically to all three modal networks.

We use NetworkX's implementation of Dijkstra's algorithm to calculate the shortest-path distance for each OD pair and mode, using edge length as a cost. Following (Levinson & El-Geneidy, 2009) circuitry \mathcal{C} was computed as the ratio of network distance to straight-line distance. We eliminate observations with circuitry greater than 5, which make up a small portion of the sample but lie well outside the main distribution, in order to prevent distortion from uncommon pathological paths. Following this filtering stage, each mode yields about 6,000 valid circuitry values (5,981 for driving, 5,989 for cycling, and 5,997 for walking in this implementation). We calculate the mean and median circuitry for each mode and distance band, annotated with mean and median lines (Fig. 1). Moreover, we use box plots and histograms with kernel-density estimates to summarize the distributions.

To facilitate replication and expansion to additional cities, all code, graphs, and figures are stored in an open, versioned repository (Kabir, 2025) available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17546011>. We do not calculate other connectivity or accessibility metrics like node degree, centrality, travel time, congestion, or safety; instead, we interpret circuitry as a geometric indicator of route directness. Therefore, rather than accurately characterizing how people now travel, our findings describe how the architecture of the existing network influences distance penalties across modes and trip lengths.

3 Findings

Across the stratified OD sample, circuitry values are low for all modes (Fig. 1). Driving has a mean circuitry of ≈ 1.27 , cycling ≈ 1.26 , and walking ≈ 1.23 ($n \approx 6,000$ per mode), with medians slightly lower in each case. Only a small number of circuitry values are higher than 1.1, with the majority falling between 1.1 and 1.4 (Fig. 1). The distributions are mildly right-skewed with a thin tail of higher-circuitry trips corresponding to paths forced around major barriers. Although the changes are slight in absolute terms (≈ 0.02 - 0.04 in circuitry, equivalent to around 100-200 extra meters on a 5 km journey), they are consistent across thousands of OD pairs and remain stable after stratifying by distance.

Fig. 1. Circuitry Distributions across Multi-modal mode

The box plots (Fig. 2) shows that the inter-quartile ranges are small and mainly overlapping. Cycling and walking have somewhat lower medians than driving, implying that non-motorized modes are at least as geometrically efficient. This indicates that routes are extremely direct for all modes of transportation due to Chicago's grid layout and frequent intersections (Barthélemy, 2011).

Fig. 2. Box-Plot Analysis of Circuitry Distributions

Figure 3 shows circuitry distributions stratified by straight-line distance band (rows) and mode (columns). Across all nine panels, the histograms are sharply peaked and right-skewed, with most trips clustered between 1.1 and 1.5, confirming that Chicago's multimodal network imposes relatively small detours. Short excursions (0-2 km) have the highest circuitry, with values of 1.376 (driving), 1.345 (cycling), and 1.294 (walking), indicating the influence of fine-scale barriers including rivers, rail yards, and discontinuous local roadways. Medium excursions (2-8 km) are more direct, with means of 1.266, 1.254, and 1.232 for driving, cycling, and walking, respectively, whereas lengthy trips (>8 km) had the highest means of 1.176, 1.171, and 1.163.

Fig. 3. Circuity Distributions by Distance Band and Mode - Driving (Blue), Cycling (Orange), Walking (Green)

Nonetheless, mean circuity values for all modes and bands remain within a limited range of approximately 1.20-1.35, showing that the network does not impose significant additional detours on cross-neighborhood or cross-town trips. The higher tails (values above ~1.6 and up to the 4–5 range) are concentrated in the short and medium panels, indicating that substantial detours are rare, localised events rather than a city-wide condition.

Together, these patterns show that: (i) Chicago’s grid offers consistently direct routes at all trip lengths, and (ii) non-motorised modes are at least as geometrically efficient as driving, with slightly more direct routes, especially for short and medium trips where walking and cycling are most relevant for policy which is a signal of strong spatial equity in network design. Comparatively, polycentric or suburban cities-like Los Angeles or Houston-exhibit higher circuity because of discontinuous street hierarchies and lower intersection densities (Craig & Ng, 2001; Gordon et al., 1986). The orthogonal grid of the in city of Chicago offers redundancy and multiple route options, thus allowing efficient connectivity across all modes. But it does not mean that geometry alone determines behavior; mode choice also depends on travel time, comfort, safety, and cost (Ewing & Cervero, 2010).

Our contribution is to show that, in Chicago, the built street layout is not the binding constraint on walking and cycling and that an open workflow can be replicated elsewhere to benchmark multimodal circuity and track how network investments reshape geometric efficiency over time.

4 Acknowledgements

This research was conducted independently by the authors using publicly available open geospatial data. All findings and interpretations are solely those of the authors.

5 Data Availability

The data used in this study are derived from OpenStreetMap (<https://www.openstreetmap.org>). The processed datasets supporting the findings are available in Zenodo at DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17546011>. If using or adapting this workflow, please cite as:

Kabir, S. M. R. (2025). Multimodal Circuitry in Chicago: Evaluating Urban Transport Network Efficiency Using Open Data (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17546011>.

References

- Boeing, G. (2017). OSMnx: New methods for acquiring, constructing, analyzing, and visualizing complex street networks. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 65, 126–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COMPENVURBSYS.2017.05.004>
- Boeing, G. (2019). Urban spatial order: street network orientation, configuration, and entropy. *Applied Network Science* 2019 4:1, 4(1), 67-. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S41109-019-0189-1>
- Boeing, G. (2022). Street Network Models and Indicators for Every Urban Area in the World. *Geographical Analysis*, 54(3), 519–535. <https://doi.org/10.1111/GEAN.12281;SUBPAGE:STRING:ABSTRACT;WEBSITE:WEBSITE:PERICLES;REQUESTEDJOURNAL:JOURNAL:15384632;ISSUE:ISSUE:DOI>
- Costa, M., Marques, M., Moura, F., Costa, M., Marques, M., & Moura, F. (2021). A Circuitry Temporal Analysis of Urban Street Networks Using Open Data: A Lisbon Case Study. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information* 2021, Vol. 10, 10(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/IJGI10070453>
- Costa, M., Valença, G., Adorean, C., & Moura, F. (2025). The relation between circuitry and mobility cultures: A study of 41 European cities. *Cities*, 166, 106087. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CITIES.2025.106087>
- Craig, S. G., & Ng, P. T. (2001). Using Quantile Smoothing Splines to Identify Employment Subcenters in a Multicentric Urban Area. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 49(1), 100–120. <https://doi.org/10.1006/JUEC.2000.2186>
- Cubukcu, K. M. (2020). Using circuitry as a network efficiency measure: the example of Paris. *Spatial Information Research* 2020 29:2, 29(2), 163–172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S41324-020-00342-W>
- Ewing, R., & Cervero, R. (2010). Travel and the Built Environment. *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 76(3), 265–294. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944361003766766>

- Giacomin, D. J., & Levinson, D. M. (2015). Road network circuitry in metropolitan areas. *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*, 42(6), 1040–1053.
<https://doi.org/10.1068/B130131P;PAGE:STRING:ARTICLE/CHAPTER>
- Gordon, P., Richardson, H. W., & Wong, H. L. (1986). The distribution of population and employment in a polycentric city: the case of Los Angeles. *Environment & Planning A*, 18(2), 161–173.
<https://doi.org/10.1068/A180161;WEBSITE:WEBSITE:SAGE;REQUESTEDJOURNAL:JOURNAL:EPNA;WGROU:STRING:PUBLICATION>
- Kabir, S. M. R. (2025, November 6). *Multimodal Circuitry in Chicago: Evaluating Urban Transport Network Efficiency Using Open Data*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17546011>
- Levinson, D., & El-Geneidy, A. (2009). The minimum circuitry frontier and the journey to work. *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, 39(6), 732–738.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.REGSCIURBECO.2009.07.003>
- Lima, F. T., Brown, N. C., & Duarte, J. P. (2022). A grammar-based optimization approach for walkable urban fabrics considering pedestrian accessibility and infrastructure cost. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 49(5), 1489–1506.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/23998083211048496;WEBSITE:WEBSITE:SAGE;WGROU:STRING:PUBLICATION>
- Pucher, J., & Buehler, R. (2010). Walking and Cycling for Healthy Cities. *Built Environment*, 36(4), 391–414. <https://doi.org/10.2148/BENV.36.4.391>